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Good practice guide

Use of the narrowband tuneable source

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed Compact Narrowband Tuneable Source (CNTS) for UV-VIS-NIR spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Compact Narrowband Tuneable Source (CNTS)

3.1. Design description

The CNTS is a combination of a high intensity fibre coupled broadband laser driven light source (Horne, et al., 2010) and an optical tuneable dispersion system; the latter rejecting all but a narrow wavelength band. The optical layout was designed using Zemax, an important consideration in the design being that CNTS would be transportable thus enabling its use as an in-field source for irradiance calibrations.

The CNTS tuneable dispersion system is contained within a 400 mm x 400 mm optical board, with the grating and the second parabolic mirror positions fixed; and the input pinhole (PH1), the first parabolic mirror (OAPM1) and the output slit (PH2) mounted on high precision micro-metric linear stages to provide the fine adjustment needed to compensate for the focal length tolerance of the parabolic mirrors. Both parabolic mirrors and the gratings are mounted on adjustable stages to optimise the mirrors' optical alignment. A motorised rotation stage, which sets the grating angle, uses a high-resolution encoder that has an accuracy of better than 0.001° . To cover the whole spectral range of interest a set of three gratings (G1, G2 and G3) optimised for three adjacent spectral ranges is utilised in the system. The selection of gratings is actuated via dedicated motorised stage bearing a set of three independent fine adjustable grating holders allowing individual optical alignment. A motorised filter wheel (FW) is placed into the collimated part of the beam path to act as order sorting long-pass optical filters and as a shutter. A few optical buffers are placed to reduce the coupling of internal stray-light of the system to the output slit. The optical configuration of the CNTS is shown in Figure 1. The spectrally filtered optical radiation emerging from PH2 is subsequently collimated by the third off-axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3). This optical relay generates a spatially uniform, elliptical beam profile at the output plane, ensuring well-defined and homogeneous irradiance across the detector active areas.

Figure 1: Optical configuration of CNTS.

3.2. Specifications

The specifications listed below refer to the current configuration consisting of an output pinhole (PH2) with a diameter of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ and with a collimating off axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3) with a focal length of 150 mm and 25 mm aperture diameter. The irradiance level can be increased by using a larger output pinhole (e.g., $500\ \mu\text{m}$), though this comes at the cost of a broader full width at half maximum (FWHM). The optimal trade-off depends on the requirements of the spectrometer to be calibrated. The beam geometry is governed by the focal length and clear aperture of OAPM3. A shorter-focal-length off-axis parabolic mirror produces a smaller collimated beam with correspondingly higher irradiance at the detector plane. Conversely, increasing the mirror aperture and focal length yields a larger collimated beam with reduced irradiance. In this guide we report the

specifications relative to two gratings G1 and G2 that have been thoroughly tested during the development. Specification of the CNTS in the IR region will be added when the full characterisation will be completed.

Optical field geometry

The collimated optical field exhibits an elliptical profile with major and minor axes of 22 mm and 19 mm, respectively. The optical beam exhibits a divergence half-angle smaller than 0.1°.

Spectral range

The NFT is designed to operate over a spectral range from 320 nm to 1650 nm. To achieve this, the CNTS is equipped with three reflective gratings (G1, G2 and G3), each optimised for a specific band:

- G1 : UV–VIS: 350 nm to 700 nm
- G2 : VIS–NIR: 700 nm to 1050 nm
- G3 : NIR–IR: 1050 nm to 1650 nm

Grating G1 UV-VIS

The grating G1 is optimised to work in the UV VIS spectral range.

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
2400	320 to 700	0.2	< 0.1

The wavelength scale is calibrated using a set of Kr Laser lines measured with calibrated wavemeter. From the measured points the wavelength scale is extended using the grating model to fit the measured data the wavelength accuracy is better than 0.1 nm [Smid 2021, Smid 2023].

The CNTS irradiance output level is measured by a predictable quantum detector (PQED) (Müller, et al., 2013) equipped with a calibrated aperture.

Grating G2 VIS-NIR

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
1200	700 to 1050	0.4	< 0.2

Figure 2: Irradiance levels using G2.

Irradiance levels above 850 nm will require a InGaAs or Ge based irradiance standards currently under development.

Grating G3 IR

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
600	1050 to 1650	0.8	< 0.4

3.3. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Alignment

Because the optical field is highly collimated, the irradiance remains largely unaffected by variations in position along the optical axis. Alignment on the plane perpendicular to the optical axis can be performed visually using the gratin zero order angle CNTS broadband brighter output beam.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 10 min should be allowed to stabilise the laser driven light source. After that period the temporal stability is better than 0.2 %.

Wavelength scale stability

The wavelength scale stability of the CNTS when it is not moved and in laboratory conditions has been measured to be better than 0.02 nm. In case of transportation the wavelength scale should be verified by coupling to the CNTS optical fibre to a laser of known wavelength.

Source control

Given the complex nature of the light machine the CNTS can be operated only using the developed LabView software.

3.4. Limitations

Non-ideal spatial homogeneity

The spatial homogeneity of the optical field was characterised using a small-area silicon photodiode (0.2 mm diameter) mounted on motorised stages enabling horizontal and vertical motion. The photodiode's photocurrent, converted to voltage, was recorded over a 25 mm × 25 mm square region centred on the illumination's geometric midpoint. The figure below shows the resulting optical field spatial distribution. The spatial uniformity around the central region is better than 3 %, except for a small area exhibiting reduced irradiance, likely caused by a local grating inhomogeneity that is currently under investigation.

Figure 3: CNTS spatial uniformity.

Irradiance levels

As mentioned earlier with an output pinhole (PH2) with a diameter of 100 μm and with a collimating off axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3) with a focal length of 150 mm and 25 mm aperture diameter the resulting CNTS irradiance levels are smaller than 1 mW m^{-2} . The irradiance level can be increased by using a larger output pinhole though this comes at the cost of a broader FWHM.

Stray Light

From the standpoint of the monochromatic purity of its optical output, the CNTS exhibits two spectral shoulders with an intensity of about 1 % relative to the peak. These shoulders extend symmetrically by approximately $\pm 6 \text{ nm}$ around the central wavelength. Therefore, when calibrating a spectrometer, the measured spectral irradiance should be integrated over a spectral interval of at least $\pm 6 \text{ nm}$ around the target wavelength to properly account for these contributions.

Figure 4: Measurement of CNTS spectral stray light with QASUME spectrometer.

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